

Helicobacter pylori and the immune system: Genetics, epigenetics and treatment aspects

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Abstract

Helicobacter pylori infects more than 50% of the human population worldwide. Persistence and colonization of this bacterium in the host result in genetic and epigenetic alteration and intra-complicated reactions that enhance innate and adaptive immune responses, which lead to the development of several gastrointestinal illnesses and increase the risk for gastric cancer progression. Even the World Health Organization (WHO) classified a bacterium in the first group of carcinogens; also, it has been associated with multiple extra gastric implications such as autoimmune disease and cardiovascular disease, thereby being considered a highly infectious pathogen and a critical health problem globally. Detection of the infection facilitates prognosis for suitable treatment that enhances eradication of this bacterium to prevent further implication. The aim of this review is to convey several aspects related to the *Helicobacter pylori* infection, to understand and clarify the epigenetic changes, host immune response, and the pathogenicity of multiple virulence factors involved in the infection, as well as diagnostic options, the fundamental strategy of treatment and the rate of reinfection among variable individuals.

Keywords

anti-*Helicobacter* therapy, epigenetics, genetics, *Helicobacter pylori*, immune system

Introduction

One of the most important gram-negative bacteria infecting over 50% of the human population worldwide is *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) (Ríos-Sandoval et al. 2024). It is a motile bacterium with flagella, which enables it to transfer a bacterial shape that prolongs survival in the host gastric mucosa, is non-spore forming, microaerophilic (needs a small amount of oxygen to grow), and spiral-shaped (this is the reason for naming *H. pylori*), with an approximate

length of 2–4 μm. It is mainly observed near the epithelial cell in gastric mucosa, and it is the most pathogenic defect in the stomach (Ansari and Yamaoka 2022).

The transmission of *H. pylori* is suspicious, even though several studies show that it can be transferred from individual to individual mostly through gastro-oral, fecal-oral, or oral-oral via either food or water contaminants or from the external environment to the individual. *H. pylori* could be obtained in early childhood mostly from mother to child either in developed or non-developed countries,

although it can persist for a long period of time if non treated properly (Öztekin et al. 2021).

Consequently, it is fundamental to clarify the pathogenesis strategies of *H. pylori* in interaction and effectiveness on the host immune defense. There are few studies about this topic. The aim of this study is to clarify the interaction between the immune system and *H. pylori* virulence factors and to describe in detail the treatment and diagnosis of *H. pylori*.

The role of *H. pylori* chemical structure in infection

H. pylori have an inner membrane consisting of thin layers of peptidoglycan, and the outer membrane has lipopolysaccharides (LPS), which have a serious role in the inflammation induction of *H. pylori* infection progression. It has a phospholipid layer, which is limited in bacteria; this chemical structure has an essential role in the pathogenicity of bacteria, particularly in escaping from the host immune response (Tang et al. 2023). Bacteria spiral-shaped also encourage bacterial colonization across gastric mucosa, then penetrate and decrease mucus viscosity through secretory enzymes such as mucinases and collagenases. These secretory enzymes will facilitate the bacteria's adhesion and binding to the receptors in the epithelial cells in the mucosal layer in the stomach by *H. pylori* adhesion molecules, which involve: blood group antigen binding adhesion (BabA, BabB), sialic acid-binding adhesion (SabA), adhesion-associated protein (AlpA, AlpB), *H. pylori* outer membrane protein (HopZ, HopQ), and lacdiNac-binding adhesion (LabA) (Xu et al. 2020; Ansari and Yamaoka 2022; Elbehiry et al. 2023; Sedarat and Taylor-Robinson 2024).

Diseases of *H. pylori* infection

H. pylori have different strategies that can be established in suitable conditions to survive, colonize, and resist stomach acidity and the immune host response which, makes it a unique and severe pathogen, in addition to the diversity of the *H. pylori* genotype. Growing in the stomach will cause infection in gastric mucosa; this consequence is due to a virulence factor by the bacteria's involvement: urease, cytotoxin-associated antigen A (CagA), and vacuolating cytotoxin (VacA) (De Brito et al. 2019). Despite most cases of acute *H. pylori* infection being asymptomatic or having few symptoms, serious infections of *H. pylori* result in several associated diseases. About 10%-15% of individuals are infected with *H. pylori*, which is involved in inflammation of gastric mucosa, even though acute and/or chronic peptic ulcer, mucosa associated with lymphoid tissue lymphoma (MALT), and serious cases contributed highly to gastric cancer (GC). Additionally, to date, there are several studies revealing that *H. pylori* contributed to extra gastric disorders like autoimmune disease, cardiovascular disease, iron deficiency anemia, allergy, different neurodegenerative disorders and thrombocytopenia (Alsulaimany et al. 2020; Elbehiry et al. 2023).

As well, the World Health Organization considered *H. pylori* as one of the most carcinogenic agents in the first class to correlate with the majority prevalence of gastric cancer (GC), which has approximately 80% globally (Lina et al. 2014). This is the reason to make *H. pylori* involvement challenges in the development and explore targeted treatment. Therefore, it is difficult to be eradicated worldwide (Öztekin et al. 2021).

H. pylori infection is distinct with several factors such as geographical locations, socioeconomic status, temperature, gender, poor sanitation conditions and age. However, *H. pylori* can infect several categories of ages: children, adults, and elderly, but the high-risk group is elderly due to their physiological body functions that decrease with age, use of multiple drugs for different diseases, and external environmental factors (Šterbenc et al. 2019).

Mechanism of pathogenicity

Mechanism of pathogenicity and degree of *H. pylori* infection supposedly regarding the several virulence factors encoded genes of bacteria and host immune response. These virulence factors induce bacterial colonization in an acidic environment in the gastric mucosa, which causes infection (Chmiela and Kupcinskas 2019) (Table 1). It has genes encoded in surface protein molecules that assist the bacteria to adhere to the host cell surface, such as blood group antigen binding adhesion (BabA, BabB), sialic acid-binding adhesion (SabA), adhesion-associated protein (AlpA, AlpB), *H. pylori* outer membrane protein (HopZ, HopQ), lacdiNac-binding adhesion (LabA), Outer inflammatory protein A (OipA), genes that cause inflammation like cytotoxin-associated gene A (CagA), vacuolating cytotoxin A (VacA), gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase (gGT), duodenal ulcer promoting gene (*dupA*), and lipopolysaccharides (LPS) (De Brito et al. 2019; Ansari and Yamaoka 2022).

Urease is the primary virulence that induces successful bacterial colonization and makes it a unique pathogen that produces and secretes enzyme; it forms about 15% of bacterial protein and is mostly used for the diagnosis of *H. pylori* infection (Ali and AlHussaini 2024). According to the translocation, there are two types of ureases inside and outside bacterial cells, even though each of them has a specific range of pH to be active and work. Ureases protect and enhance bacterial survival in the stomach that has a highly acidic pH of approximately (1.5 _2), which leads to converting the urea to ammonia (NH₃) and (carbon dioxide) CO₂ that neutralizes the pH (Tilahun et al. 2022).

(α -CA) carbonic anhydrase enzyme neutralizes the acidity in gastric mucosa by converting CO₂ to NaHCO₃ bicarbonate as a host immune response, resulting in stimulation of the immune cells like neutrophils and trigger monocytes and triggering proinflammatory cytokines (Pop et al. 2022). Although the urease is more active in bacterial spiral form than in coccid form and prolongs the production of bacteria to increase the negative impact on the gastric mucosa to increase the risk of gastric malignancy. As development of anti-*pylori* targeted therapies,

Table 1. Virulence factors of *H. pylori* and its mode of action.

Virulence factor	Mode of action
Urease	Generation of ammonia and carbon dioxide Facilitate bacterial colonization, neutralizing of acidity in the gastric epithelium Enhance the progression of tumorigenesis (De Brito et al. 2019; De Brito et al. 2019)
Flagella	Bacterial motility across gastric epithelium Bacterial colonization Induce an inflammatory response Escape immunity (Chang et al. 2018; Gu 2017)
Bacterial shape	The spiral shape of bacteria promotes its invasion across gastric epithelium Bacterial protection (Tang et al. 2023)
Bab A	Enhance bacterial attachment and colonization in gastric epithelium Incorporate into the epithelial cell receptors Trigger <i>Cag A</i> transmission (Ansari and Yamaoka 2017)
Sab A	Enhance bacterial attachment and colonization in gastric epithelium Incorporate the Silyl-Lex antigen (Elbehiry et al. 2023)
Hop Q	Trigger bacterial adherence to the gastric epithelium Induce the action of immune cells (Feige et al. 2018)
Oip A	Trigger bacterial adherence to the gastric epithelium Destroy mucosal layer of the gastric epithelium Enhance cell apoptosis (Ansari and Yamaoka 2022)
LPS (lipopolysaccharide)	Trigger the immune response Stimulation of anti-inflammatory response Obstruct mucous in gastric epithelium (Tang et al. 2023; Ansari and Yamaoka 2022)
Vac A	Vocalization of gastric epithelium Trigger cell apoptosis and necrosis Suppress phagocytosis Induce autophagy pathway Trigger tolerogenic dendritic cell Prevent effector T- cell response Enhance tumorigenesis progression (White et al. 2015)
Cag T4SS and Cag A	Suppress phagocytosis Reduce antimicrobial peptide Stimulate tolerogenic dendritic cell Prevent effector T- cell response Enhance tumorigenesis progression (Mohammadzadeh et al. 2023)
γ -Glutamyl transferase (γ -GT)	Promote pro-inflammatory molecules Enhance production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) Induction of cell proliferation Triggering the DNA damage (Sharndama and Mba 2022)
HtrA	Stimulate bacterial adherence to the gastric epithelium Involvement in <i>Cag A</i> translocation Impair the biological function of epithelial cells layer (Kabamba et al. 2018)
Phospholipase	Trigger inflammatory and immune response Obstruct mucus secretion in gastric epithelium Enhance bacterial colonization and lipid destruction (Baj et al. 2021)
Superoxide dismutase (SOD)	Activation of macrophage Trigger bacterial colonization (Stent et al. 2017)
Arginase	Inhibit T- cell proliferation Suppress ROS Enhance cell apoptosis and disrupt the immune responses (Baj et al. 2021)
Cholesterol- α -glucosyltransferase	Trigger pro-inflammatory response Preventing phagocytosis Disrupt autophagosome-lysosome fusion (Morey and Meyer 2019)
Outer membrane vesicles	Disrupt the biological function of epithelial cells Protect bacteria from ROS (Wei et al. 2022)

one of them is urease inhibitors (J. Y. Yang et al. 2021). Additionally, bacterial colonization induced by the motility of bacterial sheathed flagella across gastric mucosa at low pH, approximately (1–6). Flagella as a second virulence assisted in the early stage of bacterial infestation in

the host gastric mucosa. The number of flagella is varied through *H. pylori* strains that determine the rate of prompt movement of bacteria, with evidence that *H. pylori* strains with less motility have no effect on colonization compared to others (Krzyżek et al. 2020).

The most important virulence factor of *H. pylori* is cytotoxin-associated gene A (*Cag A*). It has an essential role in the progress of chronic gastritis, which contributed to a high risk of the upgrowth of gastric cancer (GC) and involvement in pathogenicity island (PAI) (Mladenova 2021). It is classified into two subtypes, including cytotoxin-associated gene A positive and cytotoxin-associated gene A negative. It is generated into the host cell through the Type 4 Secretion System (T4SS), resulting in increasing harmful cell morphology, structure, and function by stimulation and alternation of several signaling pathways like phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K) (MAPK) mitogen-activated protein kinase (Reshetnyak et al. 2021; Sun et al. 2023; Wang et al. 2023).

Another virulence agent that contributed to the pathogenicity of *H. pylori* infection is vacuolating toxin A (Vac A). From its name, the mechanism of action is to create vacuoles in the membrane across the epithelial cells in gastric mucosa that lead to obstructing the permeability of the cell function and induce the autophagy pathway, as the host immune response led to interaction, disruption, and the enrollment of more immune cells to the site of infection (Alexander et al. 2021). Which ultimately results in an inflammation cascade that triggers several pro-inflammatory cytokine molecules like interleukin 1 (L1), interleukin 8 (L8), and tissue necrosis factors (TNF α) that lead to gastric disease involving peptic ulcer and for a long period of time may have effectiveness for malignancy development in gastric mucosa (Ansari and Yamaoka 2020).

Several studies show that Vac A and Cag A have a correlation to the expansion of gastric cancer (GC), although clarifying and understanding this interaction facilitates exploring a novel approach to treatment strategies (Ofori et al. 2019).

Immunological aspects for *H. pylori*

There is a complex reaction between *H. pylori* and the host immune system, which gives high attention and inclusive research to illustrate this topic. *H. pylori* can induce both innate and adaptive immune responses through its virulence factors, enhancing pathogenicity (Padma et al. 2021). Once a bacterium enters the stomach, it colonizes the mucous layer of the stomach through several phases that involve bacteria resisting the gastric acidity, motility through flagella across epithelial cells covering the gastric mucosa, adhesion, binding, emission of their toxin into epithelial cells resulting in tissue destruction, and biofilm formation in order to give it high protection from immune host response and targeted antibiotics (Tilahun et al. 2022).

The interaction occurs between several virulence factors of *H. pylori* and host receptors expressed in the gastric epithelium; it includes NOD-like receptors and Pattern Recognition Receptor proteins (PRRs) (Cheok et al. 2022). PRRs are expressed in the innate immune cells, such as neutrophils and antigen presentation cells (APCs).

One of the classification is toll-like receptors (TLRs), including TLR1, TLR4, and the epithelial cells of gastric mucosa, that will recognize the pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) of the *H. pylori* in addition to lipopolysaccharide and lipoprotein (Torres and Backert 2008; Niu et al. 2020).

H. pylori bind specifically with gastric epithelium through adherence molecules involving Alp A, Alp B, Sab A, Bab A, and Bab B (Faass et al. 2023). These recognitions stimulate the innate immune response, leading to the release of neutrophils, macrophages, and lymphocytes. Another signaling molecule involved is interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), interleukin 6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) as pro-inflammatory cytokines in the site of infection to produce more immune cells and inflammation in gastric mucosa (Cheok et al. 2022).

Further signaling cascades promote more cytokine molecules like NF- κ B due to the activation of other virulence factors by bacteria, such as the insertion of Cag A among T4SS in the gastric epithelium. This leads to recruiting more immune cells toward the site of infection (Espinoza-contreras et al. 2020; Kumar et al. 2021).

The most cells involved in this process are T cells, which are differentiate to Th1 response and Th2 response. CD4+ is one of the most important T cells that have a significant role in promoting several cytokines in the gastric mucosa; also, CD8+ has a function in cancer progression (Nagashima and Yamaoka 2019).

B cells have a crucial role through the production of immunoglobulin against bacterial infections such as IgM, IgG, and IgA that can be detected in the first month of infection. *H. pylori* in a chronic state can form follicle-like structures resulting in the recruitment of T and B cells (Nakamura et al. 2011; Niu et al. 2020).

Implications of interaction induce through several bacterial evasion strategies from the immune response, such as the production of urease, inhibition of bacterial recognition by the toll-like receptors (TLR), and injection of Cag A and Vac A as virulence factors (Yang et al. 2020; Maubach et al. 2022). Furthermore, the inhibition of adaptive immune response through *H. pylori* by restricting T cell proliferation across several extent, which involve unique glycosyl cholesterol substitutes and gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase. Cag pathogenicity island (Cag PAI) encoded for T4SS stimulates several signaling pathways leading to activation of nuclear factor KB (NF- κ B), which is the significant transcription factor that acts as an immune-inflammatory in the host response for inflammatory genes (Faass et al. 2023).

The interaction between pathogens and inflammatory cells in the host will produce oxidative stress, large amounts of reactive nitrogen species (RNS), and reactive oxygen species (ROS), which cause DNA damage in the gastric epithelial cells. Finally leads to damage of gastric mucosa, resulting in severe gastric disease and increasing the risk of gastric cancer (GC) (De Brito et al. 2019; Jain et al. 2021).

Epigenetics and *H. pylori*

Epigenetics is the study of proteins surrounding the DNA rather than DNA sequences (Furuta et al. 2015). Several studies have taken attention to explain the role of *H. pylori* through epigenetic alternation in the host cells (Sualeh et al. 2024). Both epigenetics and genetics supported each other; *H. pylori* has a high degree of genetic diversity due to the recombination and mutations, which increase the potential role in the pathogenesis in the infected host. It changes from the first stage of infection to adaptation and colonization, which constitutes efforts and challenges through the development of target therapies (Nell et al. 2018).

Therefore, once the bacteria infected the host as a strategy to survive and escape from the immune response through the epigenetic process, the bacteria achieved their its purpose by impacting host chromatin modification, histone alterations, DNA methylation, and noncoding RNA, leading to gene silencing and increasing the probability for tumorigenesis development (Capparelli and Iannelli 2022).

One of the most epigenetic functions is regulating gene expression through turning genes on or off as DNA methylation; it is a significant process involving in the normal growth conditions and illnesses through monitoring signaling pathways (Vaziri et al. 2018; Muhammad et al. 2019). *H. pylori* has high genetic and epigenetic diversity, which facilitates adaptation easily in the host condition, such as the restriction-modification system (R-M). (R-M) systems could develop through decline and obtain certain genes for a long period of time. There is much research demonstrating several epigenetic and genetic changes through *H. pylori* impacts, especially chronic inflammation that induces multiple signaling pathways that change the epithelial cell behaviors in gastric mucosa, such as prefiltration and apoptosis during the infection, which play a significant role in the gastric cancer progression (Deng et al. 2022).

Recently there has been massive attention to implementing *H. pylori* pathogenicity in epigenetic alterations in the host cells. Epigenetics involves histone modifications that control DNA transcription and gene expression in specific nucleotides such as adenosine or cytosine by an enzyme called methyltransferases at a specific site, which is a CpG island where the gene is suppressed, chromatin, and non-coding RNA were reconstructed (Muhammad et al. 2019).

DNA methylation induced by *H. pylori* occurs in the promoter region of cancer- inhibited genes. Stimulation of these genes by *H. pylori* contributed to the progress of gastric cancer (Chiariotti et al. 2013; Muhammad et al. 2019). There is a study to show the levels of methylation in 8 markers of CpG islands in persons infected with *H. pylori* that have great levels of methylation (about 5.4 - to 303-fold) in the gastric mucosa compared to uninfected persons (Ushijima and Hattori 2012).

Methylation and acetylation indicators associated with *H. pylori*

There are several novel indicators linking *H. pylori* with gastric cancer involved in DNA methylation, such as *HUS1*, *GSTO2*, and *TMEM190*, through a prospective to utilize in diagnosis and development target therapy (Yousefi 2019).

DNA damage in cells activates checkpoints to inhibit the replication process and stimulate DNA repair machinery or induce apoptosis to eliminate damaged cells. Evidence studies have been demonstrating that the *HUS1* (checkpoint clamp component) protein-coding gene has critical roles in DNA damage and apoptosis associated with cancer development that involve in the ATR-dependent pathway, which is one of the significant damage checkpoint pathways. The Rad9-Rad1-HUS1 (9-1-1) complex is part of this signaling pathway; after DNA damage, this complex enhances phosphorylation of certain substrates such as Rad17, Chk1, and Rad9 to suppress DNA synthesis (Takeishi et al. 2015). Regarding Wang et al., who demonstrate the *H. pylori* alternation epigenetic changes through hypermethylation of *HUS1* leading to downregulation of its expression in the gastric cancer tissue. The *HUS1* gene is part of the DNA damage response. Hypermethylation of *HUS1* leads to decreased levels of *HUS1*, which impairs the cell's ability to efficiently repair DNA damage. This can lead to genomic instability, a hallmark of cancer development (Wang et al. 2021).

Another protein-coding gene is glutathione S-transferase omega 2 (*GSTO2*), which is one of the most important enzymes belonging to the Glutathione-S-Transferases (GSTs) family and has several cellular defense functions such as detoxification. The *GST* gene in humans has two omega classes including *GSTO1* and *GSTO2* (Terayama et al. 2020). The main function of *GSTO2* is to promote the binding of glutathione to several electrophilic substances, either endogenous or exogenous, such as oxidative stress substances. Furthermore, infection with *H. pylori* has a negative impact on the *GST* gene, either through gene deletion or induction of the active site of *GST*, resulting in defect in its function in the gastric epithelium. Furthermore, they show *H. pylori* reduction gene expression level of *GSTO2* in gastric tissue because the *GSTO2* gene allows getting rid of harmful substances. There is hypermethylation, and then its inhibition may contribute to the formation of harmful molecules and oxidative stress, which contributes to the development of cancer (Board and Menon 2016).

TMEM190 is transmembrane protein 190, the biological function currently unknown, despite the study only showing that *H. pylori* induction expression of *TMEM190*, although in gastric cancer tissue, showed lower expression. However, the decrease of *TMEM190* by hypermethylation suggests that it may be involved in maintaining normal cell function. Depletion of *TMEM190* expression can disturb cell homeostasis and promote malignant changes. In general, hypermethylation of *HUS1*, *GSTO2*, and *TMEM190* leads to their decrease, disrupting normal cell functions and leading to gastric cancer. This change in the genetic

process is a fundamental mechanism that occurs when gastric cancer develops, especially in the context of associated risks such as *H. pylori* infection (Wang et al. 2021).

Patients infected with gastric cancer due to *H. pylori* have higher levels of DNA methylation, with Cag A positive patients contrasting to the Cag A negative patients, which is proposed to be a potential role of the pathogen Cag A factor on the aberrant DNA methylation (Takeshima et al. 2017). Corresponding studies show the significant correlation between the accumulation of aberrant DNA methylation and gastric cancer (GC) through the extent of DNA methylation, which has a high risk of progression of GC as aberrant DNA methylation is indicative of the epigenetic changes by inhibition of tumor suppressor genes (Maeda et al. 2017).

Aberrant DNA methylation through *H. pylori* occurs at H3K27me₃, resulting in histone methylation. Furthermore, aberrant H3K27me₃ could be prompted through several factors like severe inflammation. With evidence that Mongolian gerbils had *H. pylori* infection, it was shown that aberrant DNA methylation in the gastric gland's cells was triggered, giving an indication that they had *H. pylori*, according to their findings (Niwa et al. 2010). In the gerbils infected with *H. pylori*, they were subjugated with an immune-inhibitory factor, which is cyclosporine A, according to their findings, which were that *H. pylori* inflammatory response conducts the aberrant DNA methylation, not actually *H. pylori* (Hur et al. 2011). Therapy: The gastric mucosa in gerbils infected with *H. pylori* showed a high degree of DNA methylation corresponding with inflammatory gene responses to the infection, which involves *IL-1b*, *Nos2*, and *TNF* (Katsurano et al. 2012).

Moreover, not only are tumor suppressor genes hypermethylated in *H. pylori* but also microRNAs (miRNAs) as non-coding genes involved in methylation. According to Choi et al.'s finding in the gastric cell lines the expression level of miR-200a/b affected by the DNA methylation (Choi et al. 2020).

Another mechanism for *H. pylori* implemented throughout infection is histone acetylation, such as at the beginning of *H. pylori* infection deacetylation of H4, which led to a negative impact on the host's particular gene expression (Orenay-Boyacioglu et al. 2018; Yousefi 2019). There are few studies that provide evidence of *H. pylori*'s impact on DNA repair via chromatin modulation in the host. Therefore, *H. pylori* have epigenetic changes through ATM regulation, regarding Santos et al.'s in vivo and in vitro findings that *H. pylori* triggers DNA damage after the ATM responses, which include hypomethylation of the promoter region and have an impact on histone H3 and histone H4 through hyperacetylation (Santos et al. 2018).

p27 tumor suppressor gene and *H. pylori*

Recent research demonstrates that AGS cells and HS3C infected with *H. pylori* have high levels of *p27* mRNA in contrast to uninfected cells, which proposed that *H. pylori*

manipulates the expression of *p27* by conducting several strategies including epigenetic monitoring at the transcription level through histone acetylation and regulating the breakdown level of *p27* (Byun et al. 2012).

p27 is considered to be a tumor suppressor gene, encoded by the *CDKN1B* gene. *p27* had been an essential role in cell cycle regulation through actions as an inhibitory implication on the cyclin- dependent kinases (CDKs). The abnormal expression level of *p27*, such as downregulation has a negative impact on the gastric epithelium behaviors in proliferation and apoptosis that enhances the development of gastric cancer (Li et al. 2021). *p27* expression is regulated in several aspects, including in response to the phosphorylation of the delta opioid receptor (DOR) signaling pathway, which triggers the downstream molecule cytoplasmic beta-arrestin1 that enrolls histone acetyltransferase p300. Then it transfers from the cytoplasm to the nucleus and gathers in the *p27* promoter; this can lead to histone 4 acetylation (H4) and finally leads to *p27* transcription. Regarding the Byun et al. in vitro study, it shows that both AGS and HS3C are infected with *H. pylori*, directly decreasing phosphorylated DOR, resulting in decreasing the enrollment of histone acetyltransferase p300. Histone acetylation has essential epigenetic strategy involvement in the regulation of *p27* transcription, which decreases the acetylation of histone 4 in the *p27* promoter that led to decreasing the expression of *p27* mRNA and *p27* protein (Byun et al. 2012; Razavipour et al. 2020).

Research has shown that *H. pylori* infection enhances the AKT/PI3K pathway that controls the phosphorylation of *p27* at T157 and T198, leading to mis-localization of *p27* in gastric cancer. Mis-localization is a poor prognostic factor in gastric cancer. It represents the first evidence for the transfer of a specific bacterial virulence factor that subsequently governs the translation of the CDK inhibitor in the host cell. This makes it particularly important because *p27* has both tumor-suppressive and cancer-promoting effects. According to its intracellular localization, the mis-localization of *p27* in the cytoplasm caused by *H. pylori* could be a major mechanistic causal relationship between *H. pylori* infection and gastric cancer. Insufficient levels of *p27* induced by *H. pylori* infection increase the resistance of gastric epithelial cells to apoptosis, thus promoting the development of cancer (Wen et al. 2011).

Cytochrome P450 (CYP450) and *H. pylori*

There are several factors that play a role in *H. pylori* resistance against the treatment, like the polymorphism of *CYP2C19*, *IL-1B*, and *MDR1* (*C3435T*) genotype in the acidic pH of a stomach (pH = 6–8). The most sensitive bacterium to the pH is *H. pylori* (Ram et al. 2019; Wang et al. 2021).

Proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) are produced by the S-mephenytoin 4-hydroxylase enzyme system related to the CYP system. It has a specific role in the antibiotic's

effectiveness related to *H. pylori* eradication through increasing the pH in gastric mucosa by reducing acid production and supporting the stability of antibiotics and stimulating their activity. S-mephenytoin 4-hydroxylase enzyme involves 38 allele variants and 9 exons (Lin et al. 2017; Lima et al. 2020).

CYP2C19 and *H. pylori*

Many enzymes act as drug metabolizers, such as *CYP2C19*, *CYP2D6*, *CYP2C9*, *CYP3A4*, and *CYP3A5*, with different polymorphisms that cause several drug impacts (Yamazaki 2017; Nguyen et al. 2024). Polymorphisms can contribute both to certain genotypes and phenotypes that are involved and related to the rate of drug metabolites and *CYP2C19* phenotype in the human. Involvement genotypes are as follows: extensive metabolizers (EM) with genotype (*CYP2C19**1/*1) have normal metabolic activity, poor metabolizers (PM) have abnormal metabolic activity (*CYP2C19**2/*2, *2/*3), and intermediate metabolizers (IM) with genotype (*CYP2C19**1) (Ahmed et al. 2016).

The liver produces an enzyme with an essential role in metabolic function for several drugs and is responsible for the utilization of the production of PPI with rabeprazole, which is cytochrome P450 2C19 (*CYP2C19*). Researchers give it attention and focus on its function regarding *H. pylori* (Kuo et al. 2014; Shah et al. 2021).

CYP2C19 polymorphisms are contributed to the outcome of drug actions, as host genetics. There are *CYP2C19* polymorphisms that include mutations in exon 4(*3) and exon 5(*2) that have an association with the *H. pylori* failure to eradicate. Smoking is a non-genetic factor contributing to *H. pylori* failure eradication. Meta-analysis shows smoking individuals prolong *H. pylori* infection compared with nonsmokers because it can alter the expression of *CYP2C19* (Kang et al. 2018).

CYP2C19 polymorphism frequency varies among ethnic individuals; a previous study shows the Asian population contrasting to the white poor metabolizer (PM) (Kuo et al. 2014; Zhao et al. 2022). Another study shows frequencies of *CYP2C19* alleles among worldwide populations, resulting in *CYP2C19**3 being mostly frequent in Asian populations, while *CYP2C19**2 is mostly found in the African and European, as well as *CYP2C19**17 found among Europeans. That demonstrates *CYP2C19* allele frequencies are variable and interethnic across the worldwide population, which could be contributed to by population history, migration, colonization of islands, genetic drift, geographical location and environmental factors (Naranjo et al. 2015).

PPI functions as an induction of the production of gastric acid, which makes it a favorable treatment for illnesses correlated with gastric acid, such as peptic ulcer. According to the FDA, there are six PPIs approved: omeprazole, esomeprazole, lansoprazole, dexlansoprazole, pantoprazole, and rabeprazole (Athanasios et al. 2017). Regarding the *CYP2C19* as a metabolizing drug enzyme, it contributed

more with omeprazole and lansoprazole, where other PPI derivatives have minimal contribution, giving the indication that *CYP2C19* polymorphism variations are more affected with lansoprazole and omeprazole. Consequently, studies supported that the *CYP2C19* genotype affected the effectiveness of therapy based on the omeprazole that plays a role on in the eradication rate of *H. pylori*. On the other hand, various research studies obtain the opposite finding that there is no association between the *CYP2C19* genotype and its effects on the PPIs like omeprazole in the eradication of the *H. pylori*, such as studies among the Jordanian population. They suggested that there are other factors having roles rather than *CYP2C19*, such as gender, age, dietary intake, use of therapies targeted to treat certain diseases, and the performance of such organs like the kidney and liver. So the results vary based on several factors, such as the ethnicity variable (Zihlif et al. 2022).

IL-1B, *MDR1*, and *H. pylori*

IL-1B polymorphisms showed effectiveness in the eradication rate of *H. pylori* infection. One research study that has been published shows that *IL-1B* has a lower eradication rate of polymorphism *IL-1B* 511 C/C in infected individuals compared with another polymorphism *IL-1B* 511 T/T and C-T (Hong et al. 2016; Luo et al. 2023).

MDR1 polymorphisms having 28 exons play a role in *H. pylori* eradication. Once PPIs are taken and after absorption in the gastrointestinal tract, *MDR1* will be transported through P-glycoprotein (P-gp), which is an ATP-dependent transporter protein (Karaca et al. 2016). Several research studies were accomplished on the *MDR1* (C343 5T) polymorphism that contributed to PPI actions and impacts on the eradication of *H. pylori* (Nguyen et al. 2024). Among Vietnamese children with *MDR1* (C3435T) polymorphism, there is a significant impact on the eradication rate of *H. pylori* infection (Thuy et al. 2024).

H. pylori diagnosis and treatment

H. pylori diagnosis

As mentioned earlier, *H. pylori* infection affected human health, either intragastrically or extragastrically disease. Although this bacterium contributed to other expanding inclusions involving metabolic syndrome and autoimmune disease, which make it difficult in diagnosis and prognosis (Elsaied et al. 2024). It is important to understand diagnosis methods to understand the pathogenesis of bacteria that facilitate, enhance, and improve effective therapy targeting to the *H. pylori* infection and reduce its prevalence rate globally (Sedarat and Taylor-Robinson 2024).

There are different diagnostic methods to detect the infection of *H. pylori*, and they are assorted into the invasive method, such as histology, fluorescent in situ

hybridization (FISH), culturing, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), rapid urease test (RUT), and non-invasive methods like serology, urea breath test (UBT), and antigen stool tests (ASTs), which vary from each other in sensitivity and specificity (Alsulaimany et al. 2020). Diagnostic tests for *H. pylori* infection are divided into two categories: Invasive techniques include endoscopic examination and gastric biopsy, followed by a combination of RUT, histology or culture, or molecular techniques on the biopsy specimens. These non-invasive techniques (UBR, AST, serological, and molecular tests) are based on the presence of pathogenic bacteria enzymes, antigens, antibodies, or DNA sequences. There are several efforts from researchers and health administration to achieve more accurate diagnostic methods to obtain more accurate results in treatment. Because the diagnostic technique for *H. pylori* identification must be tailored to the individual's specific requirements, considering test availability, expense, required accuracy, and basic clinical information. In addition, there are no independent "gold standard" tests, but a variety of techniques are widely used. Table 2 shows the general advantages and disadvantages of *H. pylori* diagnostic approaches. (Öztekin et al. 2021).

H. pylori treatment

Regarding the treatment of *H. pylori*, which has many challenging development efforts due to the behaviors of bacterial strains, such as single drug resistance or multidrug resistance, single antibiotics have no ability to cure *H. pylori* infection. So the main strategy and

recommendation for *H. pylori* treatment is combination of antibiotics. The first-line treatment is triple antibiotic approach (TAA), which involves two antibiotics at a minimum (commonly clarithromycin and levofloxacin) and one proton pump inhibitors (PPI) (Palareti et al. 2016; Zagari et al. 2017). There is another antibiotic therapy as a second-line treatment if the first line fails, which is the bismuth quadruple therapy (BQT) approach, which involves PPI, metronidazole, tetracycline, and salts. Due to the increase in the cases of antibiotic resistance, there is a novel treatment recommended as an alternative strategy that involves probiotics, organic products, phage therapy, antimicrobial peptides, vaccines and enhanced diet intake (Huang et al. 2024) (Table 3).

PPIs recommended doses are omeprazole 20 mg, esomeprazole 20 mg or 40 mg, lansoprazole 30 mg, dexlansoprazole 30 mg or 60 mg, pantoprazole 40 mg, rabeprazole 20 mg (Kaplan et al. 2019; Matsumoto et al. 2019; Georgopoulos and Papastergiou 2021; Jung et al. 2021).

Obviously, the consequences of cure and recovery from *H. pylori* infection vary from individual to individuals; that can be determined by certain parameters like bacterial virulence factors, host immunity status, and external environmental factors. In treatment, there is a recurrence term defined as the repeated infection of *H. pylori* after recovery and a reinfection term defined as the repetition after full treatment but with the new strain of *H. pylori*. There are differences from each other depending on several factors such as geographical location, ethnicity, and family history of *H. pylori* infection. In developing countries, there is a little percentage with reference to

Table 2. Several diagnostic techniques for *H. pylori* identification (Tonkic et al. 2018; Atkinson and Braden 2016; Malfetheriner et al. 2023).

Technique	Advantages	Disadvantages
Non-invasive		
Stool Antigen Test	Rapid, cheap, and simple	False negative results occur when there are trace amounts of bacteria, current use of antibiotics, bismuth subsalicylate, and proton pump inhibitors Challenges associated with sample preservation and retrieval
Urea Breath Test	Simple, safe, high accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity	False negative results due to bleeding in case of misuse of antibiotics and proton pump inhibitors Low accuracy in some cases, such as chronic gastritis and gastric cancer
Serology Test	Effectiveness in terms of cost, and ease of access Relevant to the diagnosing of individuals receiving antibiotic and PPI therapy	Inability to distinguish between acute infection and previous contact Not suitable for posttreatment verification
Invasive		
Endoscopy	Obtaining gastrointestinal biopsy samples leads to definitive identification of infection	Timeconsuming It takes a lot of experience
Rapid Urease Test	Rapid, cheap, and simple	Lower sensitivity and specificity in some cases, such as gastrointestinal ulcers, bleeding, and intestinal metastatic disease
Culture	Identifying antimicrobial resistance patterns Sensitivity	Costly Complex Laborious
Histology	The gold standard for detecting <i>H. pylori</i> in the mucosa and examining the eradication status	Monitor reliability Stressful Requires a lot of skill Very expensive
Polymerase Chain Reaction	High sensitivity and specificity No transportation requirements	False positive results due to the detection of DNA fragments from dead bacteria Require skills Expensive

Table 3. Recommended *H. pylori* treatment regimens.

Category	Therapy	Regimens	Comment
First-line therapy	Clarithromycin-based triple therapy or standard triple therapy	+Clarithromycin 500 mg	Suitable for regions with < 15% prevalence of clarithromycin resistance
		Twice daily for all antibiotics after meals	Recommended for firstline regimen
	Sequential therapy	14 Days	Recommended for firstline eradication regimen
	Concomitant therapy	Standard dose PPI + clarithromycin 500 + amoxicillin 1 g + metronidazole 500 mg	Limited to use when we have a high resistance rate of clarithromycin and metronidazole
Twice daily for all antibiotics 10_14 days		Recommended for firstline regimen for highresistance rate with < 15% prevalence of dualclarithromycin and metronidazole resistance	
Hybrid therapy	7 days dual therapy standard dose PPI + amoxicillin 1 g followed by 7 day quadruple therapy with a PPI standard dose + amoxicillin 1 g + clarithromycin 500 mg + metronidazole 500 mg	Recommended firstline option when bismuth is unavailable	
Second-line therapy	Bismuth's quadruple therapy	Standard dose PPI + bismuth 120_300 mg + tetracycline 500 mg + metroimidazole 500 mg 4 times daily for all antibiotics 14 days	Beneficial for firstline treatment
			Effected through dual clarithromycin and metronidazole Resistance
	Levofloxacin triple therapy	Standard PPI + levofloxacin 500 mg once daily, and amoxicillin 1 g twice daily 14 days	More extensive compared to concomitant
Third line therapy	Rifabutin triple therapy	PPI standard dose + rifabutin 150 mg + amoxicillin 1 g 14 days	Widely recommended as first empiric therapy in highly resistant region
	High-dose dual therapy	PPI high dose + amoxicillin > 2 gr /day for e.g., 500 750 mg 14 days	Can be used as firstline therapy if another treatment is not available
			Suitable for patients who have allergies to penicillin
			Recommended when standard triple therapy or sequential or concomitant failure
			Effective in the case of developing countries in the population with a high rate of resistance to clarithromycin, metronidazole
			Recommended as secondline therapy after the failure of firstline therapy
			Recommended as a thirdline treatment
			Rifabutin resistance is rare
			Most common as a thirdline treatment

reinfection, of *H. pylori* after restoration from the infection, also in high propagation *H. pylori* reinfection particularly in regions with have high rates of *H. pylori* due to the bacterial antibiotic resistance (Xie et al. 2020). Several studies show that bismuth quadruple therapy (BQT) has a high rate of eradication of reinfection compared with triple therapy (Choi et al. 2019). Therefore, there is intensive effort by researchers in exploring effective vaccines, which are regarded as the preferable route to solve the problem of the new *H. pylori* strain that is antibiotic resistant (Huang et al. 2024). Therefore, until now there is no effective vaccine for the eradication of the *H. pylori* infection, and it is still a big health problem worldwide (Šterbenc et al. 2019; Sedarat and Taylor-Robinson 2024). *H. pylori* reinfection rates vary in several countries, as described in Table 4. Therefore, according to the meta-analysis study in 2017, the global annual reinfection rate per person was 3.1%. Although the reinfection rate was inconsistent due to multiple factors involved: socioeconomic status, level of education, age, and percentage of family members infected with *H. pylori* (Wan et al. 2017).

Moreover, there are several antibiotic developments against *H. pylori* infection with evidence; unfortunately some of the *H. pylori* strains become impediments to the antibiotics very fast, which makes it encounter

challenges on prevention and developing vaccines (Haamadi et al. 2022). There are studies reported that *H. pylori* infection for a long period of time in some individuals has negative impacts on nutrition state, which is “malnutrition”, due to a correlation with inadequate absorption for several nutrients needed for growth, like high salt concentration. Therefore, *H. pylori* feeds on the nutrients and vitamins from blood hosts such as iron, cobalt, zinc, and lipids. Treatment for *H. pylori* is summarized in a proper diet that is rich in fruits and vegetables (Öztekin et al. 2021).

The role of vitamin D in *H. pylori* treatment

Polymorphisms in vitamin D receptors (VDR rs 2228570 and VDR rs 7975232 alleles) and the VDR gene (*Apal*, *TaqI*) play a role in *H. pylori* treatment (Abo-Amer et al. 2023).

Vitamin D has a function as an anti-inflammatory involvement in the initiation of antimicrobial action. Studies supported that vitamin D has a significant impact on the treatment of *H. pylori*, through findings established in vitro by Guo et al. that vitamin D is in biologically active form. 1a,25-dihydroxy vitamin D3 has a protective effect

Table 4. *H. pylori* reinfection rate among ethnic individuals globally.

Country	Reinfection rate annually (%)	Follow-up period	Reference
Japan	0.22	1.8-8.0 years	(Take et al. 2012)
China	1.75	1 year	(Xie et al. 2020)
Morocco	0.8	1 year	(Allah et al. 2013)
Korea	3.1	18-95 months	(Mezmale et al. 2020)
USA	8.05	2 years	(Bruce et al. 2015)
Brazil	1.8	5 years	(Silva et al. 2010)
Italy	2.33	3 years	(Jung et al. 2021)
Alaska	16.1	2 years	(Bruce et al. 2015)
India	2.4	3 year and 5 months	(Schutze et al. 1995)

toward *H. pylori* infection through acting as an immunomodulatory molecule (Zhang 2014). Furthermore, Shafirir et al. indicated that successful eradication of *H. pylori* infection can be achieved through elevated levels of vitamin D (Shafirir et al. 2021). Whereas another study shows that defect eradication of *H. pylori* infection corresponds with vitamin D deficiency (VDD) (Zhang 2015). Similar studies corresponding to Mohamed et al. results in a correlation between the eradication of *H. pylori* infection and the VDR *FokI*, *ApaI* polymorphism (Muhammad et al. 2019). Furthermore, according to Huang et al.'s findings, the vitamin D and *H. pylori* eradication rates correspond to each other (Yan et al. 2019).

Interestingly, vitamin D3 may be a novel approach as therapeutic agent against *H. pylori* via several signaling pathways driven by the vitamin D receptor, such as enhancing the phosphorylation of c-Raf/MEK/ERK by inhibiting the apoptosis of the human gastric epithelial cell line GEC-1 infected with *H. pylori*. However, it has been established that vitamin D3 plays an antimicrobial action against *H. pylori* via protein disulfide isomerase A3 receptors (PDIA3) and the STAT3–MCOLN3–Ca2+ signaling pathway, which led to stimulating the restoration function of the impaired lysosome due to the *H. pylori* infection. It has been estimated that Cathelicidin Anti-Microbial Peptides (CAMP) act as an anti-inflammatory and protective effect against *H. pylori* through the VD3/VDR complex by interacting with the promoter region in CAMP, resulting in a decrease in the damage of gastric epithelium and extra clearance of bacteria (Zhang 2015; Jiang et al. 2016; Zhou et al. 2020; Abo-amer et al. 2023).

Conclusion

In summary, our study assessed the updates regarding *H. pylori* infection, which remains a major health problem and is prevalent worldwide. The prevalence rate of infection varies among individuals according to certain criteria such as ethnicity, geographical region, and socio-economic state. Since the transmission is not clear, it is associated with multiple diseases, either gastric and/or extra-gastric diseases, and even causes genetic changes that lead to tumorigenesis in the host.

We study the exact mechanism of *H. pylori* infection in several aspects, such as pathogenesis through multiple

virulence factors, recommended treatment, polymorphisms, epigenetic changes and immune response in the host, to understand this interaction, which leads to improving the proper way of controlling and reducing the prevalence rate of this infection in different countries.

However, we believe that our study makes a significant contribution to literature because there is little research related to our topic that has been published. Our study aims to clarify the exact interaction and effect in the host.

The conclusion of the study related to the previous studies and confirmed their findings that *H. pylori* had a multi-significant effect on the host regarding the immune response and epigenetic alteration. The result demonstrates that there are complex and dynamic physiological factors involved in this interaction, either from the host or from the several virulent factors of bacteria. Besides these findings, we can reveal a novel approach against this bacterial infection.

Recommendation

We need several experiments in vivo and in vitro to further investigate the exact mechanism of infection regarding the genetic host and immune response. Furthermore, we suggest exploring effective vaccines and enhancing specific management strategies of healthcare, such as an emphasis on guidelines for water purification, personal hygiene, and control of misuse or overuse of antibiotics like amoxicillin to prevent urgent antibiotic resistance of *H. pylori* and the behaviors of patients that contributed to therapy regimen failure. There would be effective roles in preventing and controlling the outbreak, implications of the infection like cancer and reinfection, especially in regions that have high prevalence rates, such as Jordan.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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